

Kinetics of the Reaction Between Chromium Peroxydichromate and Malic Acid

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Kinetics of the reaction between chromium peroxydichromate and malic acid has been studied at various temperatures. Effect of manganese sulphate and sulphuric acid on the reaction rate has also been studied. Besides calculating total order of the reaction, temperature coefficient and energy of activation, a suitable mechanism has also been suggested to explain the reaction.

The recent review by Waters¹ on the oxidation processes in general and of some α -hydroxyacids by Mn(III)^{2,3,4}, Ce(IV)^{5,6,7,8} and Vanadium(V)⁹ throws much light on the mechanism of oxidation and its dependence on the nature of oxidant. Kumar and Saxena¹⁰ have studied the kinetics of oxidation of malic acid by peroxydisulphate.

Pillai and Rai¹¹ have observed that water decomposition product of ethyl acetate extracted blue perchromate is a peroxy compound having $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_8)_3$ formula (chromium peroxydichromate) which is similar to peroxy disulphate. Kinetics of oxidation of tartaric, citric and oxalic acids by this compound have been studied by Singh¹². A search of literature reveals that the kinetics of oxidation of malic acid by chromium peroxydichromate remains hitherto unstudied. In the present paper are presented the results of the kinetics and mechanism of the interaction between peroxidichromate and malic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chemicals used were either B.D.H., A.R. or of extra pure quality.

The blue perchromate was prepared by mixing ice cold solutions of 5% $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ (75 ml.), 2N H_2SO_4 (10 ml.) and 20 vol. H_2O_2 (30 ml.). The blue perchromate formed was extracted in ethyl acetate (50 ml.) and washed several times with ice cold distilled water. It was

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then transferred to a flask containing about 30 ml. distilled water and allowed to decompose in a cold place. The decomposition product so obtained is chromium peroxydichromate. Solutions of suitable concentrations were prepared from this solution by titrating it against a standard thiosulphate solution. Standard solutions of malic acid and manganese sulphate were prepared by dissolving exact weight in distilled water.

The solutions of malic acid and manganese sulphate of suitable concentrations were taken in 250 ml. pyrex conical flask and were placed in a bath maintained at the desired temperature within a range of $\pm 0.1^\circ$. The solution of decomposition product was placed separately in the same bath. After some time both the solutions were rapidly mixed. 5 ml. aliquots of the reaction mixture were withdrawn at suitable time intervals and the residual decomposition product was estimated iodometrically.

The calculated first order rate constants were found to be fairly satisfactory and the results obtained were quite reproducible (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1.

Effect of reactant's concentration : The effect of the concentration of the reactants on the reaction rate was studied. The results at 30° are presented in Table I. There is no effect of increasing concentration of peroxydichromate on the reaction rate. In case of malic acid the reaction rate increases with increase in concentration but the values for specific rate constant $k_s = k/(\text{malic acid})^2$ remain constant showing that the order with respect to malic acid is two.

The values obtained for 'n' by isolation method were found to be 1.76, 1.90, 1.94, 1.85, 1.99, 2.01 which shows that the order with respect to malic acid is two.

Effect of manganese sulphate concentration : The effect of four different concentrations of manganese sulphate on the reaction rate was studied and the average values of rate constants at 30° are noted in Table II.

The table shows that increasing concentration of manganese sulphate increases the rate of the reaction.

Effect of sulphuric acid : The effect of sulphuric acid on the reaction rate was studied and the average values of rate constants at different concentrations of sulphuric acid are noted in Table III.

TABLE I

Dependence on reactant concentration

Peroxydichromate (N)	Temp. °C	Malic acid (N)	$k \times 10^2$ min ⁻¹	$k^2 = \frac{k}{(\text{malic acid})^2}$ min ⁻¹ (mol ⁻² litre ²)
0.020	25	0.50	1.95	7.80
0.025	25	0.50	1.97	7.88
0.033	25	0.50	1.86	7.44
0.050	25	0.50	1.94	7.76
0.020	30	0.30	1.03	11.46
0.020	30	0.45	2.32	11.45
0.020	30	0.60	3.95	10.97
0.020	30	0.75	5.84	10.15

TABLE II

Effect of manganese sulphate

Malic acid = 0.50N

Peroxydichromate = 0.02N

MnSO ₄ N × 10 ³	First order rate constants $k \times 10^2$ min ⁻¹
Nil	2.55
2.76	3.63
5.52	3.73
8.29	4.05

TABLE III

Effect of sulphuric acid

Temp. 35°

Malic acid = 0.225N

Peroxydichromate = 0.020N

Sulphuric acid (N)	$k \times 10^2$ min ⁻¹
0.10	2.50
0.20	3.49
0.30	4.30
0.50	6.29
0.75	7.07
1.00	8.28

The observations show that the rate constant increases with the increasing concentrations of sulphuric acid.

The reaction was studied at 25, 30, 35 and 40°. The average temperature coefficient was found to be 1.70. The difference in rate constant corresponds to an energy and entropy of activation values of 9.60 Kcals. and -33.45 cal/degree mole respectively.

DISCUSSION.

Earlier workers (*loc. cit.*) have observed that different end products are obtained during the oxidation of malic acid depending on the nature of the oxidant employed.

In the present study, we detected formic acid as the oxidation product by chromotropic acid reaction¹³ and carbon dioxide was also found to be evolved. To explain these facts following mechanism is suggested.

In the first step the chromium peroxydichromate decomposes to give dichromate ion and peroxy oxygen atoms. The peroxy oxygen atoms so generated oxidise the malic acid (fast), followed by slow oxidation of latter by two hexavalent chromium atoms of the dichromate ion. The hexavalent chromium in the first stage accepts two electrons from the reductant malic acid, leaving tetravalent chromium as intermediate product. In the second stage of oxidation, the second hexavalent chromium atom again accepts two electrons from the reductant (malic acid) leaving another tetravalent chromium. These two tetravalent chromium (intermediate forms) then by mutual acceptance and donation of electrons give Cr^{+5} and Cr^{+3} and the former is then reduced to Cr^{+3} by fast oxidation of the malic acid. The above mechanism can be represented as :

The above mechanistic stage seems to be followed by the fast oxidation of formyl acetic acid formed above to formic acid as :

